

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Phthalic Acid in Aquo-ethanolic Mixtures

P. K. BISWAS^a, S. C. LAHIRI^{b*} and B. P. DEY^c

^aUnited Bank of India, 507, R. B. C. Road, Garifa, North 24-Parganas

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Vivekananda Mission Mahavidyalaya, Viveknagar, P.O. Chaitanyapur (Haldia)-721 645

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As in aqueous solutions, potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (0.05 M) may be used as a suitable buffer in mixed solvents also, provided the first and second dissociation constants of phthalic acid in mixed solvents are known. The first dissociation constants have been determined using solubility and conductometric measurements and the second ones have been determined pH-metrically.

The quantitative measure of the ion-solvent or solute-solvent interactions have been obtained from the values of Gibbs energy of transfer of phthalic acid, biphtalate ion and phthalate ion by coupling solubility values of H₂Ph and the dissociation constant values using appropriate relations. $\Delta G_i^0(\text{HPh}^-)$ and $\Delta G_i^0(\text{Ph}^{2-})$ have been found to be increasingly unfavourable in going from water to non-aqueous solvents. The Λ^0 values of H₂Ph and KHPH also decrease continuously in going from water to mixed solvents.

Non-aqueous and mixed aquo-organic solvents have been increasingly used in analytical chemistry, in organic and inorganic syntheses and for studying reaction kinetics^{1,2}. The H⁺ ion concentration is one of the important parameters for studying the physicochemical properties in mixed solvents. Unfortunately, the lack of suitable buffers in mixed solvents appears to be the main constraint in the measurement of H⁺ ion concentrations in mixed solvents. It is therefore desirable to find ways and means to prepare standard buffers in mixed solvents. Potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 M) is a widely used standard buffer for aqueous solutions. Naturally, it is tempting to utilise it as a standard buffer in different mixed solvents. It necessitates the determination of the dissociation constants of phthalic acid in mixed solvents. This led us to determine the first dissociation constant of phthalic acid in ethanol-water mixtures conductometrically. But the second dissociation constant can not be determined conductometrically, which we determined pH-metrically. The results are reported in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The first dissociation constant of phthalic acid,

$$K_1 = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} \cdot C_{\text{HA}^-}}{C_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}} \times \frac{f_{\pm}^2}{f_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}} \quad (1)$$

was determined by the solubility method³. Accurate values of K_1 were determined using the method of computation suggested by Fuoss and Kraus^{4,5}. The equation is

$$\frac{F(Z)}{\Lambda} = \frac{1}{K_1 \Lambda^{\circ 2}} \times \frac{\Lambda c_{\pm}^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^{\circ}} \quad (2)$$

Since the solutions are extremely dilute, $f_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}$ can be taken to be unity. Considerable uncertainty is known to exist in the Λ^0 values obtained from intercepts using equation (2). The accurate values of phthalic acid were obtained from the relation,

$$\Lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{A}} = \Lambda_{\text{HClO}_4}^{\circ} + \Lambda_{\text{KHA}}^{\circ} - \Lambda_{\text{KClO}_4}^{\circ} \quad (3)$$

The values of $\Lambda_{\text{HClO}_4}^0$ and $\Lambda_{\text{KClO}_4}^0$ were taken from our works⁶.

The Λ^0 values of KHA in different solvent systems were obtained from the plots of Λ_{KHA} at different concentrations against \sqrt{c} and subsequent extrapolation to zero concentration.

The values of the Onsager constants

$$\sigma = 82.4/(\epsilon T)^{1/2}, \eta \text{ and } \theta = 8.20 \times 10^3/(\epsilon T)^{3/2}$$

were calculated utilising the values of the viscosity coefficient and the relative permittivity ϵ of the aquo-organic mixtures from literature^{1,7}. The σ , θ and Λ^0 values were utilised to calculate

$$Z = \frac{(\theta \Lambda^0 + \sigma) \sqrt{\Lambda c}}{\Lambda^{3/2}}$$

and $F(Z)$ values. The limiting Debye-Hückel equation was used to calculate,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = A \sqrt{\alpha c} \quad (4)$$

with appropriate values of A in mixed solvents ($\alpha = \Lambda/\Lambda^0$). The slopes were calculated by iteration using the method of least-squares. The values of the slope were accepted only when the values of the regression coefficient were better than

0.995. From the slope and the known Λ^0 value, the K_1 values of phthalic acid in aquo-organic mixtures were determined.

The second dissociation constants,

$$K_2 = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{A}^{2-}}}{C_{\text{HA}^-}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{A}^{2-}}}{f_{\text{HA}^-}} = K_2' \times f_{\text{A}^{2-}}$$

were determined pH-metrically. The measured H^+ ion concentrations of neutralised solutions of KHA were utilised to determine K_2' . However, in order to get the thermodynamic dissociation constant K_2 (using activities) the following equation is used,

$$\log K_2 = \log K_2' + \log f_{\text{A}^{2-}} \quad (5)$$

$$= \log K_2' - AZ_1^2 \sqrt{\mu} + C \mu$$

or,

$$\log K_2' - AZ_1^2 \sqrt{\mu} = \log K_2 - C \mu \quad (6)$$

The left-hand-side of the equation was plotted against μ to get $\log K_2$ or K_2^8 .

The $\text{p}K_1$, $\text{p}K_2$, Λ^0 and solubility values of phthalic acid at 298.15 K are given in Table 1. The precision of $\text{p}K_1$ values is 0.01 in water

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY, EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES AND DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF PHTHALIC ACID IN EtOH + H₂O MIXTURES AT 290.15 K

EtOH wt%	1/ε × 10 ²	A	Solubility* mol dm ⁻³	Corrected pH	Λ ⁰ (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² equiv ⁻¹)			Phthalic acid	pK ₁ **	pK ₂
					HClO ₄ (Ref. 6)	KClO ₄ (Ref. 6)	KHPH			
0.0	1.27	0.509 0	0.037 61 (0.037 62)*	2.23	416.6	140.4	119.20	395.40	2.95 (2.96)	5.43 (5.43)*
8.0	1.35	0.555 2	0.044 44	2.26	372.0	116.9	92.12	347.22	3.27 (3.16)	5.70
16.4	1.42	0.613 0	0.068 38	2.27	301.5	95.0	72.46	278.96	3.44 (3.39)	5.97
25.3	1.53	0.693 9	0.111 0	2.20	250.0	78.5	58.14	229.64	3.51 (3.49)	6.47
34.4	1.71	0.791 2	0.145 3	2.16	196.0	66.0	45.45	175.45	3.54 (3.55)	6.81
44.0	1.90	0.927 0	0.288 9	2.08	172.6	58.2	40.24	154.64	3.72 (3.73)	7.24
54.1	2.14	1.133 0	0.548 7	2.05	142.0	52.0	36.30	126.30	3.95 (3.98)	7.49
64.7	2.44	1.348 0	0.615 4	2.08	118.0	49.5	34.36	102.86	4.14 (4.13)	7.82
76.0	2.87	1.707 0	0.642 27	2.30	108.0	48.6	32.89	92.29	4.50 (4.59)	8.33
87.6	3.37	2.179 0	0.661 5	2.52	92.0	48.0	31.90	75.90	5.02 (5.06)	-
100.0	3.95	2.792 0	1.135 9 (1.1357)*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*Solubility and pK₁ in parenthesis taken from Ref. 9; **pK₁ value in parenthesis from solubility measurement.

to 0 ± 0.03 in higher percentages of alcohol. The solubility values can be regarded to be accurate within 0.1–0.25%.

The Gibbs energy changes of transfer for the first and second dissociation of phthalic acid from water (W) to solvent (S) were calculated from the equations,

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(1) = -2.303 RT [\log K_1(S) - \log K_1(W)] \quad (7)$$

and

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(2) = -2.303 RT [\log K_2(S) - \log K_2(W)] \quad (8)$$

The Gibbs energy changes of transfer of neutral acid were calculated from the equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}_2\text{A}) &= -2.303 RT \log \frac{M_S}{M_W} \cdot \frac{f_S(\text{H}_2\text{A})}{f_W(\text{H}_2\text{A})} \\ &\approx -2.303 RT \log \frac{M_S}{M_W} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where M_S and M_W are the molar concentrations of H_2A in the saturated solutions of phthalic acid in the solvent (S) and water (W) respectively. The activity coefficients of neutral H_2A in the standard states of the respective solvents had been assumed to be unity. Appropriate corrections were made for the dissociation of the acid while calculating M_S and M_W .

Table 1 shows that the solubility of phthalic acid increases with increase in organic solvent, and the solubility values obtained in the present work in water and ethanol agree well with the literature values⁹. However, the correlation of the solubility values with different types of interactions (as suggested by Shinoda¹⁰) could not be made.

The effect of solvent on the dissociation of phthalic acid as reflected in the change of its dissociation constants (Table 1) is likely to be related to the solute-solvent interactions but no useful correlation can be made with solvent property. The aquo-organic solvents are characterised conspicuously by the change in relative permittivity (or dielectric constant) and relative basicity. Increase in basicity upto about 72 wt% of alcohol^{11,12}

(the basicity of ethanol + H_2O mixtures can be regarded to be maximum in this region) should increase the dissociation of the acid but the dielectric effect is more powerful to decrease the dissociation leading to a continuous increase in pK values and the effect is more pronounced in the case of the second dissociation of the acid. However, in absence of ΔH and ΔS data, the structural aspect of the solvent effect could not be predicted. Though the transfer Gibbs energy change gives some idea regarding the solvent effect on the dissociation of the acids, better idea may possibly be derived from the single ion Gibbs energy changes and they may be calculated in the way given in our previous communications^{3,6,13,14} from the equation,

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(1) = \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{HA}^-) - \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}_2\text{A}) \quad (10)$$

or,

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{HA}^-) = \Delta G_t^\circ(1) - \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}_2\text{A}) \quad (11)$$

and

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{A}^{2-}) = \Delta G_t^\circ(2) - \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^\circ(\text{HA}^-) \quad (12)$$

Since $\Delta G_t^\circ(1)$, $\Delta G_t^\circ(2)$ and $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}_2\text{A})$ are experimentally determined quantities, the uncertainty in the single ion values arises mainly from $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values determined using extrathermodynamic assumptions^{11,12} with inherent limitations. Thus, the single ion values can never be absolute but give the trend of their relative variations with solvent composition, being collectively dependent on the solvent basicity, polarisability, refractive index, dielectric constant and a host of other variable properties of unknown magnitude.

The $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values are taken from the works reported elsewhere^{11,12}. The $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values are in qualitative agreement with the values reported by Popovych¹⁵ based on TABBPh₄ (triisoamylbutylammonium tetraphenylborate) but disagree with the recent values reported based on TATB (tetraphenylarsonium tetraphenyl borate)¹⁶. However, the $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values obtained using TATB do not correctly describe the solvent properties. Moreover, it is always advisable not to use water as a 'reference standard' when TATB is used.

Thus, in spite of uncertainties, the $\Delta G_i^0(\text{HA}^-)$ and $\Delta G_i^0(\text{A}^{2-})$ values (Table 2) are increasingly positive, the higher values of $\Delta G_i^0(\text{A}^{2-})$ indicate greater resistance of the ion to go into solution. But the monotonic increase in $\Delta G_i^0(\text{ion})$ values with solvent composition shows that the dielectric effect is predominant and it must be larger for the phthalate ion. The Gibbs energy of transfer though increasingly favourable for the uncharged acid must be increasingly unfavourable for the ions.

Though we could not determine the second dissociation constant of H_2A using H_2 -electrode, the K_2 values determined using glass electrodes are accurate and may be utilised to calculate the $p\alpha_{\text{H}}^*$ of the buffer solution of 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate (KHPH) in aquoethanolic mixtures. The $p\alpha_{\text{H}}^*$ ¹⁷ of the 0.05 M KHPH buffer solution in aquo-organic solvents would be

$$p\alpha_{\text{H}}^* = \frac{1}{2} pK_1 + \frac{1}{2} pK_2 - 2 \log f_{\pm} \quad (13)$$

It would be desirable to prepare 0.05 M KHPH buffers and to measure pH-metrically the H^+ ion concentrations in different aquo-ethanol mixtures of known H^+ ion concentrations and to compare the two values. Even the first dissociation constant K_1 alone of phthalic acid may be utilised to prepare suitable buffers.

Comparison of Λ^0 values of phthalic acid and KHPH in aquo-ethanol mixtures is not possible in view of the lack of conductance data in mixed solvents. However, the Λ^0 values of HPh^- in aqueous solution at 298.15 K comes out to be $45.6 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, comparable e.g. to the value $44.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ for HCO_3^- ion¹⁸ in aqueous solution at 298.12 K. Thus the Λ^0 values of the acid and the salts appear to be in order.

The variation of the Walden product of electrolytes with solvent composition is known to provide information regarding ion-solvent interactions. Therefore, attempts have been made to examine the variation of the Walden product ($\Lambda^0\eta_0$) with solvent composition (Table 3). It is found that the Walden products ($\Lambda^0\eta_0$) pass through a maximum at about 8 wt% of alcohol and then decrease continuously. The initial increase in viscosity and $\Lambda^0\eta_0$ with addition of ethanol is known to be due to strengthening the 3D-structure of water causing an increase in viscosity values which subsequently decreases due to the breakdown of 3D-structure of water beyond 44 wt%. However, the proton jumps in aqueous solution gradually decrease with addition of ethanol resulting in an enormous decrease in Λ^0 which outweighs the viscosity increase even upto 44 wt% of ethanol. Thus, $\Lambda^0\eta_0$ decreases continuously with increasing ethanol concentration. However, nothing specific can be said about

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER (KJ mol^{-1}) OF ANION ($\Delta G_i^0(\text{A}^{2-})$) OF PHTHALIC ACID IN $\text{EtOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ MIXTURES AT 298.15 K

EtOH wt%	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$ (Ref. 12)	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}_2\text{A})$	$\Delta G_i^0(1)$	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{HA}^-)$	$\Delta G_i^0(2)$	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{A}^{2-})$
8.0	-1.08	-0.41	1.83	2.50	1.48	5.06
16.4	-1.83	-1.48	2.80	3.15	3.14	8.12
25.3	-2.70	-2.69	3.20	3.21	5.88	11.79
34.4	-3.38	-3.35	3.37	3.40	7.93	14.71
44.0	-4.52	-5.05	4.40	3.87	10.44	18.83
54.1	-5.53	-6.64	5.71	4.69	11.81	21.94
64.7	-5.63	-6.93	6.79	5.49	13.64	24.76
76.0	-5.53	-7.03	8.85	7.35	16.72	29.60
87.6	-4.66	-7.11	11.81	9.39	-	-

In H_2O , $\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}_2\text{A}) = 8.13 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G_i^0(1) = 16.83 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G_i^0(2) = 30.98 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$.

solute-solvent interactions from Walden product measurements; single ion conductance values may give more insight and these aspects need further study.

TABLE 3—WALDEN PRODUCTS OF ELECTROLYTES AND PHTHALIC ACID IN EtOH + H₂O MIXTURES AT 298.15 K (MOLECULAR VALUES $\Lambda^0\eta_0$)

EtOH wt%	η_0 (cp)	HClO ₄	KClO ₄	K-hydrogen phthalate	Phthalic acid
0.0	0.890	3.708	1.245	1.061	3.519
8.0	1.420	5.282	1.660	1.308	4.930
16.4	1.695	5.110	1.610	1.228	4.728
25.3	1.959	4.898	1.538	1.139	4.499
34.4	2.215	4.341	1.462	1.007	3.886
44.0	2.345	4.047	1.345	0.944	3.626
54.1	2.276	3.232	1.184	0.826	2.875
64.7	2.113	2.496	1.047	0.727	2.175
76.0	1.843	1.990	0.896	0.606	1.701
87.6	1.498	1.378	0.719	0.478	1.137

Experimental

Phthalic acid and potassium hydrogen phthalate (G.R., E. Merck) were used as such. These were heated at 110° and kept in a vacuum desiccator. Succinic acid, HClO₄ and NaOH used were of G.R. grade (E. Merck). Triple-distilled conductivity water from all-glass distilling set (Corning) was used for preparation of solutions. Precautions were taken to avoid contamination as far as practicable.

Absolute alcohol (B.C.P.W., India) was treated with adequate quantity of preheated CaO, kept overnight and distilled. The distillate was treated with metallic Na, refluxed and distilled, and the middle fraction was collected for use.

Solubility of phthalic acid in water and mixed solvents was determined in a Campbell solubility apparatus¹⁹ in the way described in our earlier communications^{3,6,13,14}. The concentration of phthalic acid was determined titrimetrically against standardised NaOH solution. The H⁺ ion concentration of the saturated solutions in aqueous and aquo-organic solvents were determined pH-metrically. For the measurement of H⁺ ion concentrations in mixed

solvents, the glass electrode was calibrated in mixed solvents using the standard procedure²⁰⁻²⁴

For the determination of the first dissociation constant of phthalic acid in different solvents, conductances of solutions of different concentrations (2×10^{-2} to 5×10^{-4} M) of phthalic acid and potassium hydrogen phthalate were measured. The second dissociation constants of phthalic acid were determined pH-metrically by measuring the H⁺ ion concentrations of neutralised solutions of potassium hydrogen phthalate of known concentrations. Conductance was measured with a Leeds-Northrup 4959 conductivity bridge with a sensitivity of 0.1%. A 50 cycle or 1000 cycle signal was employed. A Leeds-Northrup conductivity cell was fitted into a double-walled corning vessel containing the experimental solutions. The cell constant (0.84 cm^{-1}) was determined in the way suggested by Jones and Bradshaw²⁵. The measurements were carried out at 298.15 K.

The pH-metric measurements was made using an Orion pH-meter (model E_ATM 940 expandable ion analyser) having an accuracy of 0 ± 0.001 pH unit. The glass electrode was calibrated in aquo-organic mixtures before use in the way suggested by Van Uitert *et al.*²⁰ and used extensively by others²⁰⁻²⁴. The meter readings of the 10^{-4} M HClO₄ solutions in aqueous (taken as 4) and mixed solvents were measured to get the 'correction factor' $\log U_H$ in different solvent systems in the usual way,

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H \quad (14)$$

where, $-\log[H^+]$ and B (meter reading) represent the stoichiometric H⁺ ion concentrations of 10^{-4} M HClO₄ in aqueous and mixed solvents respectively.

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